

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BHATTA****FIRST NAME: SHIV****PROGRAM CODE: DGG****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Writing essay (EUCLID 2021, 6-7)
2. Organizing your ideas (EUCLID 2021, 9)
3. Some rule of thumb for writing a paper (EUCLID 2021, 12-14)
4. American VS. British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
6. Chicago style and usage (EUCLID 2021, 44)
7. Conclusion

INTRODUCTION TO ACADEMIC WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

ACA-401D provided a lot of valuable information on how I should get prepared for other courses that I will be taking to pursue my degree in global governance. This very first course is quite valuable for me as it guides me on how to study, analyze, and write properly. Selecting what is very useful from so many paragraphs, pages, and topics is another important lesson for me from this course. Though I was aware of some of the differences in the words between US and UK English, so much of differences in pronunciation, meaning, and spelling were some of the new things in this course. This course, reviewed by Prof. Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma, can help me to improve for professional writing.

For my response, I have decided to choose writing an essay, organizing your ideas, American vs British English, plagiarism, Chicago style, and finally conclusion.

2) **WRITING ESSAY**

Although I used to write essays at least till my bachelor's course, I have not heard of academic essays as such. I realized that this is like writing academic papers that we used to write during most of our courses. This course is quite helpful for me to provide an idea to write from the beginning to the end. How to make my writing more evidence-based is another area that I learned from the course (EUCLID 2021, 8). To be more structured, providing adequate quality time with commitment and thorough research is important. However, at the same time, unnecessary over information might also be tedious and of less value.

3) **ORGANISING YOUR IDEAS**

Once we gather a lot of information from other sources, presenting these learnings also needs good skills as these might bring a lot of questions to my mind (EUCLID 2021, 9). Brainstorming is important to bring all the possible questions so that we can present things that are in mind in a sequence and in a systematic way to convince and satisfy myself and the readers. There are nearly 50 pages in this course, and selecting a few topics and their key message is a challenge. This course provided me with ideas as to how to select topics and contents for my first response paper.

4) **SOME RULE OF THUMB FOR WRITING A PAPER**

This provided me with an idea for writing a quality paper. I realized, though I have spent quite a lot of time in writing, that there is a lot more to grasp to improve myself on how to stress the main theme of the writing and critically take it forward throughout the paper (EUCLID 2021, 13). If I am not very clear, my writing may dilute the key part is another lesson from this. We should be serious enough and ensure originality, and the reader should feel that it is adding some additional knowledge.

5) **AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH**

English is not my mother language, and I have been learning almost for over the last 60 years. I have heard of some differences between American and British English in terms of words and pronunciation. But such a huge difference I had never imagined, and it really surprised me (EUCLID 2021, 26). I will try my best to choose one of them for writing so that it is consistent.

6) PLAGIARISM

This clearly tells us that we should be ethical while writing any research paper as we are not able to generate all the required information because there are ample findings for which we do not need to reinvent the wheel (EUCLID 2021, 34). Hence, we largely depend on the findings of others to broaden our knowledge. We should be honest and give due credit to those who have, through their lot efforts, generated such knowledge. For all the information, whether it is any source related to data, quote, or visual, we must give due credit with all the details of date, author, publisher, etc. However, we do not need to give credit or cite globally accepted facts or widely used realities.

7) CHICAGO STYLE

To document our views and findings, there is a need for a style. There are many styles; whatever style we choose, we must be consistent while writing academic papers, whatever style we follow (EUCLID 2021, 41). Chicago Style, explained here, is the style I am reading for the first time. Chicago style will be useful for my writing in days to come, which provides information right from how to start writing, such as abbreviations, title, subtitle, to bibliography.

8) CONCLUSION

I joined this program and initiated reading the first course as an introductory to understand how to read or learn, analyze, and write critically. The different aspects of going through academic papers or research are captured based on one's need and utilized in one's own papers. Honestly, I realized that there is a lot more to understand to improve my writing skills. This course has helped me to better understand this, and it will be useful for upcoming courses as well.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University

Cleenewerck, Laurent, Director. 2021. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Vimeo.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.